

Analysis of Labor Compliance Execution in the RMG Sector of Bangladesh: Attempting to Meet SDG-8

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Abstract:

The RMG or ready-made garments are among the few sectors that are currently flourishing in Bangladesh. Considering the significant contribution of this sector the economic growth of Bangladesh, this sector has a high probability of playing a vital role in achieving the SDGs or the Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG-8. This goal has the objective of achieving sustainable employment and economic growth along with full and productive employment. This highlights some notable conflict while also providing attention to the significance of universal labor rights. The proportion of forced labor in the official and informal industries has significantly increased in the current situation. RMG factories should also appropriately concentrate on the Decent Work indicators for achieving SDG-8. This study aimed to examine the compliance status of the RMG industry with ILO norms and decent work indicators. These factors might play a vital role in establishing SDG-8 through Decent Work in the RMG sector of Bangladesh. Hence, we prepared a questionnaire related to compliance issues regarding ILO conventions to conduct our research work. We collect feedback from 245 different RMG industry personnel in Bangladesh. We applied the chi-square test to conduct an appropriate analysis of our collected dataset to justify the execution status of labor compliance in the RMG sector.

Keywords: Compliance, Decent work, Forced labor, ILO, Labor law, Trade Union

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1. Introduction

International labor laws are the result of a growing global awareness of the need for action on certain problems, including guaranteeing safe working conditions for agricultural workers or offering maternity protection to working women [18]. The improvement of global work principles at the ILO is a special regulative interaction that includes delegates of states, laborers and businesses from all through the earth [30]. A unique worldwide supervisory framework supports international labor standards and guarantees that the agreements adopted by each country are put into effect [12]. In the event that nations encounter difficulties implementing standards, the ILO attempts to support them by means of social consultation and technical guidance [25].

Bangladesh, an ILO member nation, has supported the Decent Work (DW) objectives since the outset of the program. The “Decent Work” initiative of the International Labor Organization has focused on creating opportunities to obtain productive work conditions of freedom, equity, security, and human dignity for women and men [5]. Since the introduction of the SDGs, which included “Decent Work” as a key component, the agenda has acquired increased support. As a result, SDG lenses offer the current Decent Work Country Program (DWCP) direction for selecting goals and priorities. The Bali Declaration, which called on governments, labor unions, and owners' associations in the area to support inclusive growth, social justice, and decent work, was also strategically aligned with the DWCP. The announcement was made during the ILO Asia Pacific regional meeting in December 2016. To date, Bangladesh has carried out two DWCPs, which span the years 2006–09 and 2012–2015. [27]. The current DWCP, which will be executed from 2017 to 2020, will be focused on outcomes, targeted, and organized with national strategy forms and international expansion ingenuities. These initiatives have been developed through

extensive stakeholder discussions with a wide variety of stakeholders and additional pertinent parties, which have formed the foundation for a participatory assessment of the country's current challenges [14].

Since the SDG is very important in the RMG sector and, most importantly, is a new concept, very little research has been conducted on this topic. In various qualitative studies, respondents provided their own answers, which were irrelevant for completing statistical analysis [3]. However, in this study, the survey was administered in an appropriate way through binary questions with close-ended yes/no answers. Investigating the challenges and barriers that hinder the effective execution of labor compliance measures on the RMG side is crucial [28]. This could include examining factors such as regulatory gaps, enforcement issues, or resistance from industry stakeholders. Moreover, the assessment of the long-term sustainability of labor compliance initiatives that leads to lasting improvements in labor standards and economic growth is another issue to be discussed. Anticipating and addressing emerging trends in the RMG sector that may affect labor compliance efforts and SDG-8 attainment, such as automation, sustainability, or changes in consumer preferences, can also be investigated [24]. Many studies have not focused on generating specific, evidence-based policy recommendations for enhancing labor compliance in the RMG sector, indicating the need for adjustments or interventions to better connect the industry with SDG-8 objectives.

Execution and achievement will depend on nations' own reasonable improvement strategies, plans and projects and will be driven by nations [4]. The SDGs will be a compass for adjusting nations' arrangements to their worldwide responsibilities [26]. Broadly claimed and country-drove practical advancement procedures will require financing strategies and resource mobilization. This study aimed to prioritize the barriers to implementing SDG-8 standards in Bangladeshi RMG factories by identifying the execution status of compliance issues and developing an interrelationship among the variables via the chi-square test.

Here, we list several research questions that are covered in this study (RQs):

RQ1: Is there any punishment in your company/industry as a penal offense for illegal exaction of forced or compulsory labor?

RQ2: Is your factory aware of the 'Modern Slavery Act 2015'?

RQ3: Is there any kind of discrimination in terms of racial, social, national or religious aspects in your workplace?

RQ4: Does your collective bargaining agent involve practicing policies and procedures in writing to protect children from any kind of exploitation?

The goal is to accomplish the following research objectives (ROs) in a manner that addresses the research questions:

RO1: To determine the execution status of labor compliance according to the ILO Conventions.

RO2: To verify whether factories want to accomplish SDG-8 by implementing decent work factors for compliance.

RO3: To determine an agreeable way to develop an adequate solution to ensure the proper level of labor for achieving SDG-8 in RMG factories in Bangladesh.

The remainder of this paper is arranged as follows. A review of the literature is presented in Section 2, and a thorough explanation of the methodological strategy and the complete logic of all pertinent operations is given in Section 3. The results and data analysis are presented in Section 4. A thorough analysis of the study's conclusions and consequences is provided in Section 5. In Section 6, the research is concluded with an outline of its limitations and a call for additional research directions.

2. Literature Review

The ILO's constituent governments, employers, and labor organizations draft legal documents referred to as international labor standards that define essential workplace norms and rights [10]. While recommendations function as nonrestrictive guidelines, agreements (or procedures) have the force of law agreements that restrict international settlements, which may be accepted by specific states. The basic conditions that sanctioning nations must fulfil are outlined in the Convention. Moreover, by adding more significant guidelines for its execution, a related recommendation strengthens the Convention [18].

2.1 Sustainable Development Goals

Sustainable development goals are international initiatives to address poverty, save the environment, and enhance the opportunities and quality of life for all people worldwide [23]. The 17 goals were adopted by the UN General Assembly, which took place in 2015 as a component of the UN's 2030 Schedule for Sustainable Development, which also included a fifteen-year plan for achieving the goals. While there has been progress in many areas at the

moment, in general, the rate and breadth of action in achieving these goals have not been fully met. A decade of intense action must begin in 2020 to accomplish these goals by 2030 [7].

2.2 SDG-8: Decent Work and Economic Growth

SDG-8: Economic growth and decent work

The goals of SDG-8 are inclusive, sustained, and sustainable growth in the economy; full and productive employment; and decent work for all. It highlights the reciprocal benefits of social, economic, and environmental policies and full employment with decent work [29]. The twelve interrelated SDG-8 targets have largely made slow progress. There are large gaps, and regional growth has not always been steady. Some notable emerging economies have experienced extremely rapid economic development and expansion, while others have lagged further behind. Numerous areas do not meet the standards for equitable and feasible growth in their economies. Despite many improvements, many employees have employment opportunities that are lucrative [16].

To promote long-term, equitable economic growth, access to financial services must also increase. To accomplish SDG-8, an established strategy that emphasizes the objectives of economic development for society, the economy, and the earth calls for inclusivity and resource decoupling [15].

2.2.1 Policies needed to achieve SDG-8 implementation

According to the Global Civil Society Report (given on the 2030 Agenda and the SDGs), several policies were presented to accomplish SDG-8. These are described below:

- To put the 2030 Agenda into practice, apply international labor standards, such as those pertaining to social dialogue, collective bargaining, and freedom of association.
- Establish all-encompassing employment policy frameworks and provide labor market institutions with support.
- To create green jobs and a low-carbon economy, implement a "just transition."
- Controlling corporate power: guaranteeing corporate responsibility, openness, and "due diligence" in international supply chains

Source: Paola Simonetti, International Trade Union Confederation (ITUC) [11].

2.3 Decent Work

"Women and men's decent employment opportunities that are profitable in environments that promote human dignity, freedom, and security" is how the International Labor Organization (ILO) defines decent work, a definition endorsed by the global community [22]. The ILO's 2008 Announcement on Social equity for a Fair the rise of globalization endorses four of the goals of the fair Work Agenda. The following topics are covered: (i) the creation of jobs, (ii) social protection, (iii) international labor standards, and (iv) social dialogue and tripartism.

This decent work initiative was founded in 2008 with the goal of assisting participants in assessing the state's implementation of decent work and generating comparable information for the analysis and formulation of policies [20]. The Government, the National Coordination Committee for Workers Education, the Bangladesh Employers' Federation, and the ILO worked closely together to develop the Bangladesh DWCP. In accordance with national strategy forms and worldwide progress creativities such as the Sustainable Development Goals, this DWCP is driven by targeted outcomes [2].

The survey will be carried out from 2017 to 20 years, with a focus on four major goals and outcomes that will aid in achieving the objectives and main goals of the 7th Five Year Plan (FYP) [21]. The DWCP is pertinent to the following targets in this context:

- Streamlining actual GDP progress over the Plan period
- Dropping the headcount proportion of scarcity
- Expanding the proportion of jobs in the manufacturing field can assist many insecure people and recent workers in finding legitimate positions in occupations
- Aggregate productivity and financing access for urban SMEs
- Enhancing the environment, disaster management and climate change
- Promoting female enrollment in technical and vocational education

2.4 ILO Convention

The ILO initially acknowledged eight "fundamental" Conventions as essential workplace rights and principles, including the effective outlawing of child labor, the freedom and right of association, the acknowledgement of the

right to bargain collectively, and the outlawing of prejudice according to employment and occupation [6]. These ideas were also covered in the ILO Statement on Fundamental Rights and Principles at Employment (1998) [13].

This adoption can assist in addressing these issues in achieving SDG-8 through decent labor since it strikes a balance between employment and economic goals while taking social impacts into consideration. At the yearly International Labor Conference, conventions and recommendations are drafted by businesses, delegates from governments, and employees [1]. Article 19(6) of the ILO Constitution mandates that after a standard is set, member states must submit it for review to their responsible authority, typically the Parliament, within a year. This refers to the conventions' potential for ratification. A Convention typically enters into force for a country one year after it is ratified, if it is. Ratifying nations commit to incorporating the Convention into their national regulations and procedures and to periodically reporting on how well it is being implemented. If necessary, the ILO offers technical support. In addition, countries might be subject to representation and complaint processes for transgressions of a convention they have ratified [17].

2.4.1 Convention 4: Abolition of Forced Labor

The Abolishing of Forced Labor Convention, 1957, is one of the eight major conventions of the International Labor Organization. It is also known as the Convention Concerning the Abolition of Forced Labor, 1957; No. 105. Some forms of forced labor were still permitted under the Forced Labor Convention of 1930. Examples of these include retaliation for taking part in strikes and punishment for having certain political beliefs. The convention concerning the Abolition of Forced Labor outlaws these. The Special Action Program to Combat Forced Labor was established to carry out the 1930 Convention on Forced Labor and the 1957 Convention Abolishing Forced Labor [8].

Convention No. 105, Abolition of Forced Labor Convention, 1957, is the ILO write-down that has been ratified the most. There are four fundamental principles and rights at work that are covered by the International Labor Organization's 1998 Declaration on the Four Fundamental Principles and Rights at Work. One of these steps is the elimination of all forms of forced labor. All members of the organization make a commitment to "respect, promote, and think, with integrity and belief" this promise. A comprehensive and productive response to forced labor encompassing prosecution, victim protection, and prevention within the larger framework to encourage decent work can be gained from the years-long observations of the ILO supervisory bodies as well as from experience acquired via technical interaction with the member nations [19].

3. Methodology

The methodology adopted for this study is a quantitative survey study. This study was conducted by administering a set of questionnaires containing dichotomous questions to various factory personnel (entry, mid and top level) based on compliance status with ILO conventions in the RMG industry of Bangladesh to help achieve SDG-8 through decent work. After receiving the responses, we obtained the primary data and the total responses, which were all approximately 245. Among the 245 respondents, 79 were from the entry level, 156 were from the mid-level level and the remaining 10 were from the top level of different textile factories. According to these data, we identified several reasons for forced labor and the violation of fundamental labor rights in various factories. The information and data collected were arranged so that further study and analysis could be performed. This study helps us to identify whether there is any forced labor or contravention of labor rights in Bangladesh and what should be done by different companies to eliminate these issues in a systematic manner.

Figure 1 illustrates the detailed methodology of this study.

To complete the study, ten dichotomous questions related to compliance with the four decent work indicators were asked of the respondents, and after that, from the given responses, a chi-square hypothesis test was performed to determine the correlation among the variables. The dichotomous questions and feedback percentages of the answers (yes/no) from 245 respondents from different RMG factories in Bangladesh are presented below:

RQ1: *Is there any punishment in your company/industry as a penal offense for illegal exaction of forced or compulsory labor?*

In response to this question, 68% of all respondents stated that in their company, punishment is available as a penal offense for illegal exaction of forced or compulsory labor, while 32% of respondents mentioned that there is no such punishment represented in

Figure 2.

Figure 1. Research methodology

Figure 2. Pie chart of the total yes/no percentage

The percentage of employees at various companies that produce RMG who say yes or no to a given RQ is expressed in Table 1.

Figure 3 - Bar diagram of the total yes/no percentage

Table 1 - Yes/no percentage of a specific respondent level

Position at work	Yes	No
Entry-Level	51.89%	48.10%
Mid-Level	62.82%	37.17%
Top-Level	90.00%	10.00%

The following **shows the** bar diagram of yes/no percentage of a particular RQ from a specific level of employees of various RMG factories in Bangladesh:

shows the bar diagram of yes/no percentage of a particular RQ from a specific level of employees of various RMG factories in Bangladesh:

Table 2 lists the total yes/no percentage, yes/no percentage of entries, and mid- and top-level responses to all the survey questions.

The questions are first listed below:

1. RQ1: Is there any punishment in your company/industry as a penal offense for illegal exaction of forced or compulsory labor?
2. RQ2: Is there any discrimination against racial, social, national or religious aspects in your company?
3. RQ3: Do pregnant women receive their maternity leave on time with promised benefits at your workplace?
4. RQ4: Is your factory aware of 'Modern Slavery Act 2015'?
5. RQ5: Is the salary/wage structure of your company based on national laws or regulations?
6. RQ6: Do you have any policy to prevent discrimination in the workplace?
7. RQ7: Does your collective bargaining agent involve practicing policies and procedures in writing to protect children from any kind of exploitation?
8. RQ8: Is there any active labor union/trade union in your organization for the sake of worker welfare?
9. RQ9: Is there any protest from the trade union or a group of employees when workers remain unpaid?
10. RQ10: Is there any PC (participation committee) in your factory to ensure compliance?

Table 2 - Yes/no percentage of respondents from various RMG factories

Sl. No.	Questions	Total Yes/No percentage		Yes/No percentage of three levels of respondents					
		Yes	No	Entry Level		Mid-Level		Top Level	
				Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
1.	RQ1	68%	32%	51.89%	48.10%	62.82%	37.17%	90%	10%
2.	RQ2	19%	81%	18.98%	81.02%	18.58%	81.41%	20%	80%
3.	RQ3	89%	11%	87.34%	12.65%	89.74%	25.00%	90%	10%
4.	RQ4	74%	26%	69.62%	30.37%	75.00%	25.00%	90%	10%
5.	RQ5	84%	16%	70%	30%	80.76%	19.23%	100%	0%
6.	RQ6	64%	36%	59.49%	40.50%	62%	38.00%	70%	30%
7.	RQ7	62%	38%	60.75%	39.24%	61.53%	38.46%	60%	40%
8.	RQ8	68%	32%	67.08%	32.91%	66.66%	33.33%	70%	30%
9.	RQ9	69%	31%	69.62%	30.37%	54.48%	45.51%	80%	20%
10.	RQ10	68%	32%	54.43%	45.56%	72.43%	27.56%	90%	10%

4. Results and Data Analysis

After all the above questions were collected, the total response (yes/no) percentage of all the dichotomous questions was calculated and is presented in **Table 3**.

Table 3 - Total yes/no percentage of three level respondents from all questions

Entry Level		Mid-Level		Top Level	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
60.93%	39.07%	64.40%	35.60%	76%	24%

Figure 4 shows the bar graph of the total yes/no percentage of all the questions from three levels of employees of various RMG factories in Bangladesh:

Figure 4 - Bar diagram of the total yes/no percentage of all respondents

4.1 Statistical analysis of the survey questionnaire

The assessment of the compliance status of RMG industry ROMC and Decent Work indicators required to achieve SDG-8 status was performed by analysing the categorical variables of the survey questionnaire through the chi-square test.

The following formula is used to compute the chi-square statistic:

$$\chi^2 = \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Here,

O = Observed value

E = Expected value

- The cross-tabulation approach yields the expected value, which is subsequently subtracted from the observed count to determine the difference between the two. Next, to eliminate the negative values, the square of the difference is computed. Next, the expected count is divided by the square of the difference.
- We must ascertain the experiment's degrees of freedom (df) before moving forward. A basic guideline for comparing samples is to use the following formula:

$$df = (\text{number of columns} - 1) \times (\text{number of rows} - 1)$$

[The rows and columns that contain the total are not included]

- After that, the chi-square (χ^2) value was calculated. If the (χ^2) value is less than the critical value or the P value is greater than the significance level, then the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This means that we will accept the null hypothesis. The critical value is obtained by observing the table of chi-square distributions for a certain df (degree of freedom). The P value was measured at a significance level of 0.05 by the chi-square test.

The assumed hypothesis of the research is as follows:

- **Null hypothesis (H0):** Since the variables have no discernible relationship with each other, feedback from the entry, middle, and top level respondents is not relevant for determining the RMG factories in Bangladesh's current state of compliance.
- **Alternative hypothesis (H1):** There are significant relationships among the variables, which means that the feedback of the respondents (entry level, mid-level, top level) is useful for assessing the current status of compliance with RMG factories in Bangladesh.

The respondents' (entry level, mid-level, top level) feedback from all the questions regarding compliance was calculated to assess the respondents' current status of compliance. For that reason, observed and expected values were determined to determine the significance of the relationship. The P value was measured at a significance level

of 0.05 by the chi-square test. Finally, the measurable chi-square (χ^2) value was compared with the critical value to measure the acceptability of the null hypothesis.

Below, the observed values in the tables are given to determine the expected values of ten questions via the cross tabulation method, after which the chi-square values are calculated for comparison with the critical values and P values:

RQ1: *Is there any punishment in your company/industry as a penal offense for illegal exaction of forced or compulsory labor?*

Table 4 describes the different values of a particular RQ from the feedback of the respondents needed to calculate the value of the chi-square for the hypothesis test:

Table 4 - Observed, expected and chi-square values from the feedback of question 01

Observed values (O)	Feedback from Question-01		
Job position	Yes	No	Grand Total
Entry level	41	38	79
Mid-level	98	58	156
Top level	09	01	10
Grand Total	148	97	245
Expected values (E)	Feedback from Question-01		
Job position	Yes	No	Grand Total
Entry level	47.722	31.277	79
Mid-level	94.236	61.763	156
Top level	6.040	3.959	10
Grand Total	148	97	245
Chi-square value [(O-E)²/E]	Feedback from Question-01		
Job position	Yes	No	Grand Total
Entry level	0.946	1.444	2.391
Mid-level	0.150	0.229	0.379
Top level	1.449	2.211	3.661
Chi-square value	6.432		
Critical Value	5.99		
Value of P	0.040		

Here, the degree of freedom is $(3-1) \times (2-1) = 2$

Significance level=0.05, so the critical value is 5.99 [from chi-square table].

The aforementioned chart indicates that the P value is less than the threshold of significance ($0.040 < 0.05$) and that the chi-square value is greater than the threshold for significance ($6.432 > 5.99$).

Comment: Null hypothesis is failed to be accepted. This is why the alternative hypothesis is accepted. According to the responses, the possibility of a punishment system for illegal exaction of forced or compulsory labor in factories is satisfactory.

5. Discussion and Implications

Like for the first dichotomous binary question, the remaining nine questions were evaluated by the same methodology as that used in

Figure 1.

The chi-square test was performed for all the questions concerning the acceptance status of the null hypothesis, and the alternative hypothesis can be found here in the following **Table 5** [the critical value is 5.99 according to the chi-square distribution at a significance level of 0.05]:

In this table, the following symbols are used for the critical value, chi-square value, P value and significance level.

Critical value: α

Chi-square value: β

P value: ρ

Table 5 - Comparison of the null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis

Sl. No.	Questions	Chi square value	P value	Comparison among the values	Acceptance status of null hypothesis	Acceptance status of alternative hypothesis	Significant relation between categorical variables (with comment)
1.	RQ1	6.432	0.040	$\beta: 5.99 > \alpha: 5.99$ and $\rho: 0.040 < \mu: 0.05$	Rejected	Accepted	(Yes)
2.	RQ2	0.0937	0.954	$\mu: 0.954 > \rho: 0.05$, $\beta: 0.0937 < \mu: 5.99$.	Accepted	Rejected	(No)
3.	RQ3	0.32	0.852	$\alpha: 0.32 < \beta: 5.99$ and $\rho: 0.852 > \mu: 0.05$	Accepted	Rejected	(No)
4.	RQ4	2.19	0.326	$\alpha: 2.19 < \beta: 5.99$ and $\rho: 0.326 > \mu: 0.05$	Accepted	Rejected	(No)
5.	RQ5	6.741	0.034	$\alpha: 6.741 > \beta: 5.99$ $\rho: 0.034 < \mu: 0.05$	Rejected	Accepted	(Yes)
6.	RQ6	0.430	0.806	$\alpha: 0.4305 > \beta: 5.99$ $\rho: 0.806 < \mu: 0.05$	Accepted	Rejected	(No)
7.	RQ7	0.019	0.990	$\alpha: 0.019 < \beta: 5.99$ $\rho: 0.990 > \mu: 0.05$	Accepted	Rejected	(No)
8.	RQ8	0.070	0.965	$\alpha: 0.070 < \beta: 5.99$ $\rho: 0.965 > \mu: 0.05$	Accepted	Rejected	(No)
9.	RQ9	6.694	0.035	$\alpha: 6.694 < \beta: 5.99$ $\rho: 0.035 < \mu: 0.05$	Rejected	Accepted	(Yes)
10.	RQ10	10.164	0.006	$\alpha: 10.164 < \beta: 5.99$ $\rho: 0.006 < \mu: 0.05$	Rejected	Accepted	(Yes)

After the respondents responded to all ten questions, the null hypothesis was rejected; therefore, there were significant relationships among the variables for these four questions, as illustrated in

Figure 5.**Figure 5 - Comparison of acceptance percentages between the null hypothesis and alternative hypothesis**

6. Conclusion and recommendations

The whole compliance effort demonstrates that national settings do not prioritize fundamental labor regulations in the same manner. Regarding efficacy and accessibility, certain requirements under specific rights contexts are widely promoted, while others are not. In this paper, we can see that most of the companies in Bangladesh are trying to maintain compliance with the ILO standards by maintaining the fundamental rights of both male and female workers, which is one of the key indicators of SDG-8.

6.2 Limitations and future scopes of the study

There are a few limitations to take into account when analysing the study's findings. The results might be inaccurate due to the reserveness and indecisiveness of the respondents when talking about their company policies. Thus, there might have been some limitations in this study that affected the accuracy of the results. Moreover, some of them lacked knowledge about the questions.

The questionnaire used in this study was developed specifically on the basis of five, seven and eight no. targets of SDG-8 among the twelve indicators. However, there are additional critical problems related to the other SDG-8 indicators, such as maintaining per capita economic growth, enhancing productivity through technological innovation and diversification, enhancing the strength of local banking systems, and creating and implementing an international plan for hiring young people.

It would be convenient if there were some options to answer the questions in a descriptive manner by implementing descriptive research so that the respondents could answer the questions properly and effectively.

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